

Protocol of the systematic review on tilting table tests of masonry assemblies

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) 2020

1.1 Introduction

A transparent systematic review should present completely and accurately why it has been done, what has been done and what was found. The benefits of a systematic review are:

- They allow to identify future research priorities based on the synthesis of state-of-the-art knowledge in a certain field.
- Questions that cannot be addressed by individual studies can be answered by systematic reviews.
- Give a hint to future studies to rectify aspects of primary research identified on them.
- Provide answers to how and why a particular phenomenon occur based on the generation and/or evaluation of theories.
- They can generate or evaluate theories about how or why phenomena occur.

The PRISMA 2020 [1] methodology, although mainly developed and used in the medical and clinical sciences, could be also applied in engineering, as it provides guidance in methodologies to identify, select, appraise and synthesize the available literature. This document presents the protocol adopted to perform a systematic review for the “Tilting Table Tests of Masonry Assemblies” European Project Semester¹ following the checklist provided by PRISMA and guidelines of the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration [2].

1.2 Protocol

The recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol according to the PRISMA methodology are presented in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Administrative information

Title:	Identification Update	Protocol of the systematic review on tilting table tests of masonry assemblies -
Registration:		In accordance with the guidelines, our systematic review protocol was registered in the Open Science Framework (OSF) Registries on October 17, 2023, registration number ezrkt, DOI: https://osf.io/ezrkt [3].
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Contributions	Alejandro Jiménez Rios is the guarantor, he supervised the work. All other authors contributed evenly to all different stages of the work.
Amendments	All authors read, provided feedback, and approved the final manuscript. In the event of protocol amendments, the date of each amendment will be accompanied by a description of the change and the rationale. See Annex A.
Support:	
Sources	This systematic review has been done within the European Project Semester program, at Oslo Metropolitan University.
Sponsor	The research has not received funding.
Role of sponsor/funder	-

Table 2. Introduction.

Rationale:	In previous research, tilting table tests have been used as a key method for evaluating the seismic response characteristics of diverse masonry assemblies. The fundamental concept involves placing a masonry assembly onto a level surface that is tilted on one of its sides. This inclination causes the masonry assembly to rotate and experience an equivalent horizontal force, simulating the dynamic forces generated during an earthquake. At a specific tilting angle, the masonry assembly reaches a critical point and experiences failure or collapse. This maximum tilting angle can be correlated with horizontal accelerations, providing insights into the structural safety and integrity of the masonry assembly. Understanding the data can lead to conclusions that may help in the preservation of historical masonry buildings. Moreover, the results from prior experiments have served as a benchmark for researchers seeking to validate various numerical modeling techniques.
Objectives:	The aim of this systematic review is to collect and synthesis state-of-the-art knowledge and information about tilting table tests performed in masonry assemblies. To this end, the proposed systematic review will answer the following questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the existing tilting table designs used to test masonry structures? 2. How can we utilize existing data on masonry failures under tilting tests to gain insights? 3. Which types of masonry assemblies have been most frequently studied in research involving tilting tables?

Table 3. Methods.

Eligibility criteria:	Apart from the keyword queries we will include a few limits on our searches in our review. Firstly, we will only be considering conference papers, journals, and articles all of which must be peer reviewed. To be included the research will need to be written in English or have a published English translation version. Also, we will only include research from 2010 or newer. If they did not meet these standards, we automatically excluded them. Also, if we find they are irrelevant topics during the screening phase, they will be removed then.
Information sources:	All databases were searched at September 13, 2023. The databases we include are Scopus, Web of science, IEEE Xplore and Engineering Village. Other search engines we include are Google Scholar and Wiley Online Library.
Search strategy:	The search was conducted in a trial-and-error method to narrow down the results to a manageable amount. First, we will begin with keyword searching and from there apply filters across all search engines to get relevant results. The first filter applied was the mode of research, where we only accepted conference papers and research journals. Then we limited the publication year to 2010 and newer and limited the language to English. If the database allows for it, we will implement a peer review. Due to time constraints, we decided to exclude the database Oria, which is Oslo Metropolitan's University's own database, because it gave us too many (448) results for this review. Further details of the search strategy can be found here [4].
Study records:	
Data management	A shared folder in OneDrive has been created and shared with all authors of the systematic review. This will be used to store data from all the selected papers from the search process.

Selection process	Each author is responsible for determining which papers to include by assessing their compatibility and relevance to our study. Moreover, each one is responsible for extracting data from the research and uploading it to the master excel sheet in OneDrive.
Data items:	From the selected research we will record the metrics of each tilting table studied including their dimensions, material, tilting mechanism, and tilting measurement device. We will collect data on the experimental methods of tilting rate and planar direction of tilt. Record will be kept on the type of masonry assembly tested including pattern and material types (photos should be included if available), and the scale of the assembly. Additionally, we will report the maximum tilting angle where failure was observed in the test. If it is deemed essential to the research's understanding, we will include the numerical validation data that certain authors may include.
Outcomes and prioritization:	The most important data to categorize is what type of tilting table was used, including the level of complexity and the data collection process. It will also be extremely important to categorize what types of structures were being tested, and to keep a record of the frequency of appearance in studies.
Risk of bias in individual studies:	Not applicable.
Data synthesis:	Our research team will be using the software Mendeley to manage our references. This software will assist us in the collection and storage of data found in our systematic review. Mendeley will be utilized to spot and remove any duplicate work. Once this is complete the screening stage will begin. The first screening stage will be based on Title-Abstract-Keywords. This screening process will be done by five people. All records will be split evenly in half so that two people can independently screen each half. The fifth person will be used as an independent party responsible for reviewing the team's work and rejecting any irrelevant research. Then during the second screening stage, we will review the whole record content in search of relevant information for the review as specified in the Dependent variable(s) / outcome(s) / main variables section. For this screening stage, the work will be divided evenly and independently reviewed by the five people involved and reviewed by the research supervisor.
Meta-bias(es):	No meta-bias analysis is envisaged at this stage of the systematic review.
Confidence in cumulative evidence:	No confidence assessment plan will be used for the proposed systematic review. This is based in the fact that no universally accepted methodology is available for the grading of reviewing in the engineering field.

References

1. Page, M.J., et al., *The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews*. BMJ, 2021. **372**: p. n71 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
2. Page, M.J., et al., *PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews*. BMJ, 2021. **372**: p. n160 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>.
3. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Systematic Literature Review on Tilting Table Tests of Masonry Assemblies*. 2023, OSF. <https://osf.io/ezrkt>.
4. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Search strategy of the systematic review on tilting table tests of masonry assemblies*. 2023, Zenodo: Online. <https://zenodo.org/records/10016521>.

Annex A

Table 4. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	18/10/2023	Initial version.

